

**BUREAUCRACY REFORM POLICY:
A CASE STUDY OF BKKBN REPRESENTATIVE
IN SOUTH KALIMANTAN PROVINCE, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

This study aims to describe the implementation of a bureaucratic reform policy in South Kalimantan Province's BKKBN Representative. A qualitative approach has been adopted in order to investigate the policy implementation process. This research instrument seeks to create a thorough description of each meaning and words, a detailed report of the respondents. It consists of three stages: observation, interviews, and documentation. Analysis of the data includes reduction, display and verification. The results of the study describe the implementation level, the decision of the Head of the BKKBN and is followed by the release of the Decree of the Chief Representative of South Kalimantan Province BKKBN Number 15/HK.02.02/J1/2018 regarding the Bureaucracy Reform Team BKKBN South Kalimantan province. The BKKBN representatives of South Kalimantan Province are expected to continuously socialize and communicate the Bureaucracy Reform Policy that involves all ASN. This is specific to the development of staffing, so that ASN better understands the aims and objectives of bureaucratic reform.

Keywords: policy, reform of the bureaucracy, change

1. Introduction

Bureaucracy, as a system of a formal organization, was mentioned by Max Weber in 1947. According to him, the bureaucracy is ideal for all types of formal organizations. The characteristics of organizations that follow the bureaucratic system are the division of labor, specialization, orientation impersonal, hierarchical authority, regulations, long career, and the main goal of the efficiency. The bureaucratic system is meant to achieve optimum working efficiency. According to Weber, bureaucratic organization can be

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used as an effective approach to control human work and the arrival at the goal. This is possible because the bureaucratic organization has a clear structure of distribution of power to the employee who have power influence to give the order and priority to their tasks (Denhardt, 1984).

Bureaucracy term, in our country, Republic of Indonesia, is often perceived as a complicated issue, which consumes long time, implies a lot of counters and phases that must be passed. Bureaucracy often is depicted as having not very enjoyable aspects, as long as the government not only not remained silent but wanted to make an effort to fix the problems in the field of public administration (Mustafa, 2013; Subarsono 2005). The years passed, government alternated measures from an old era with ones from the new era. But it was not been able to change the model of bureaucratic services. This strengthened the negative public opinion against the government bureaucracy.

in Indonesia, bureaucracy does not have a strong foundation in putting on the highest the interests of citizens as "customers" that should be served quickly and precisely (Haning, 2015). Reforms of the succession of leadership and political reforms that swept the country of Indonesia since 1998, determined an impact on reorganization of all fields.

The reform agenda is essentially an attempt to reform and determine fundamental changes to the system of governance, especially concerning institutional aspects (organization), management (business process) and human resources personnel. Reform of the bureaucracy is also an attempt to create a set of bureaucratic apparatus that can work and serve in mangkus (effective) and sangkil (efficient). To conduct towards bureaucracy mangkus and sangkil, the government seeks to make improvements through the development of services, cut regulations and requirements. Bureaucracy, including apparatus bureaucrats (government officials) in this context, should position themselves as part of the solution and provide a way of solving the impasse encountered in the process.

Ideal bureaucracy termed by the government is clean, strong and dignified, and kemangkusan creation of the effectiveness of the service. Sangkil is an Indonesian term that is rarely used, sangkil means efficient, which prioritizes high capabilities in order to optimize the utilization of various sources of funding and human resources that exist, while mangkus also a term of the Indonesian language, is rarely used even endangered, mangkus means effective, it refers to the achievement of specific targets with precise timing and clean. During the era of the Reformation period in Indonesia, various forms of improvement have been implemented in order to seat a more democratic life continues.

In Indonesia, the program of reforms contains the duties, the functions and authority run by the ministry of state and administration apparatus (Sjafrizal, 2016).

The program of reforms is applied to all ministries and agencies. The implementation of bureaucratic reform in Indonesia is regulated by Presidential Decree no. 81/2010 concerning the Grand Design Reforms 2010-2025. Furthermore, for the technical guidelines was issued another Presidential Decree in the form of Regulation of

the Ministry of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform (Kemenpan & RB) no. 20/2010 on the road map for reforms between 2010-2014. Bureaucratic Reform Program in Indonesia has been implemented two phases, the first phase has been implemented in the period 2010 and ended in 2014. Currently, Indonesia is ending the second phase of bureaucratic reform that began in 2015 and ended 2019 to come.

The program of reforms in its second phase, is stipulated in the Regulation of the Ministry of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform (Kemenpan RB) No. 11/2015 concerning the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map 2015-2019, which contains explanations Grand Design Reforms second phase (2015-2019). Road map became a reference for the ministries, institutions and agency in carrying out bureaucratic reform in their respective organizations, including the BKKBN. BKKBN institutions need to reform the bureaucracy, besides it is the mandate of the Ministry of State Apparatus Empowerment (Kemenpan RB). This is also a way to reorganize the personnel resources including performance and discipline.

Reforms implementation of the first phase, starting in 2011, has formed Bureaucracy Reform Team of BKKBN defined by regulation head of BKKBN 131/KEP/B5/2011. The Bureaucracy Reform Team BKKBN set the formal document BKKBN reforms roadmap between 2011-2014. Later a 2015 road map for reforms has been implemented for the second phase (2015-2019). The legal basis for their implementation is the BKKBN regulation number 303/PER/B4/2015 on the road map reforms BKKBN Year 2015-2019, which was subsequently updated by the Chief Regulation No. 9 of 2017 on Reforms Roadmap.

The regulation was strengthened by the decision of the head of BKKBN number 304/KEP/B4/2015 dated December 23, 2015, on Bureaucracy Reform Team BKKBN, which subsequently updated by the Decree of the Head of BKKBN No. 87/KEP/B4/2017 on Bureaucracy Reform Team. Furthermore, the level of South Kalimantan province, head of BKKBN Decree No. 87/KEP/B4/2017 on the Bureaucracy Reform Team followed up with the release of Decision Chief Representative, South Kalimantan Province BKKBN No. 15/HK.02:02/J1/2018 on Bureaucracy Reform Team BKKBN South Kalimantan province. In the Decree issued earlier in 2018. The membership structure consists of a chairman, secretary, and members, besides, there are also 6 (Six) working group (WG) consisting of Working group change management, working group Setup Procedure, working groups structuring management system apparatuses, the working group to strengthen supervision,

The decision of Chief Representative of South Kalimantan Province BKKBN No. 15/HK.02:02/J1/2018 on Bureaucracy Reform Team South Kalimantan Province BKKBN is a decision of the Head of BKKBN Representative Bureaucracy Reform Team Kalsel on the first phase of the period from 2015 to 2019, while the decision of the Head of BKKBN Representative Bureaucracy Reform Team Kalsel on the second stage according to the researchers was never issued, consequently no bureaucratic reform working group team working to carry out the implementation of reforms. Since the issuance of a decision by the South Kalimantan Province BKKBN No. 15/HK.02:02/J1/2018 on

Bureaucracy Reform Team BKKBN South Kalimantan Province, based on observations of researchers until now had never been done on a meeting working group.

Beginning with the team's ability to perform their duties, working groups were *mangkus* (effective) and *sangkil* (efficient). This assumption raises fundamental questions for evaluating an optimal reform of the bureaucracy. At the beginning, there was a lack of understanding of the environment of ASN Representative of South Kalimantan Province. Reforms understanding were still limited to the provision of benefits in performance (*tukin*) or so-called benefits of remuneration. This article describes how the implementation of the reform of the bureaucracy was made in the South Kalimantan Province BKKBN Representative and their capability to understand the reforms.

2. Research Methods

A qualitative approach is a research procedure that produces descriptive data from the words written or spoken by the people and from behaviors that can be observed. This approach is directed at the background of the individual holistically (whole) (Burhan, 2001). So, in this case, it should not isolate individual or organization into a variable or hypothesis, but it needs to be looked at as part of a wholeness. This qualitative approach is more specifically directed at the use of the case study method. As that qualitative approaches can also be referred to or qualitative case study, the research depth and detail about everything related to the subject of research (Nasution, 2003).

Thus, the researchers conducted the exploration, interpretation, and analysis of data directly without being represented. Therefore, the researchers were able to describe the strategic steps undertaken Representative of South Kalimantan Province BKKBN in implementing reforms in the institution. Some informants mentioned in the study were the Head KS/PK, the Head of KB/KR, Kasubbid Finance & BMN, Kasubbid Kespro, Kasubbid Balnak & Hanlan, and lecturer. Representative offices involved on research were located in South Kalimantan Province BKKBN. Besides, this research is also done with several objects that are considered to represent the implementation of the reforms.

Data collection was conducted through three stages, namely:

- 1) observation at representative office BKKBN on South Kalimantan province,
- 2) interviews were conducted with several informants, senior officials of Echelon IV and Echelon III, and a lecturer who were considered the master research problems,
- 3) documentation in the form of personnel data, decrees, the mutual relationship or interaction events conducted by researchers at the research object, as well as during the study process.

The data analysis technique used in this research is data analysis techniques of Miles and Huberman, namely: reduction of data as the electoral process, focusing on simplification, abstraction, and data transformation arising from the court records.

3. Results and Discussion

The results that have been obtained from the implementation of bureaucratic reform in the first stage (2010-2014) became the basis for the implementation of bureaucratic reform in the second stage (2015-2019). Therefore, the implementation of the bureaucratic reform 2015-2019 period was the strengthening of the bureaucracy reform BKKBN in previous stages. The legal basis for the implementation of the second phase of Bureaucratic Reform (2015-2019) was head of BKKBN Regulation number 303/PER/B4/2015 on the Road Map Reforms BKKBN Year 2015-2019, which was subsequently updated by the Chief Regulation No. 9 of 2017 on the Roadmap Reforms, Head of BKKBN regulation is strengthened by the decision of the Head of BKKBN number 304/KEP/B4/2015 dated December 23, 2015 on Bureaucracy Reform Team BKKBN,

Based on the secondary data retrieval field, the head of BKKBN decree No. 87/KEP/B4/2017 on the Bureaucracy Reform Team followed by the decision of the Head Representative of South Kalimantan Province BKKBN No. 15/HK.02:02/J1/2018 on Bureaucracy Reform Team BKKBN South Kalimantan province. Discharge Decisions Chief Representative, South Kalimantan Province BKKBN No. 15/HK.02:02/J1/2018 on Representative Bureaucracy Reform Team South Kalimantan Province BKKBN has become a basic reference in the implementation of Representative Office Reforms in South Kalimantan Province BKKBN.

In the decrees issued earlier in 2018, the membership composition of the team Reforms Representative BKKBN South Kalimantan consists of Chairman, Secretary and Members, in addition there are also 6 Working Group consisting of:

- 1) management of change working group,
- 2) setup procedure working group,
- 3) the working group for the reform the human resource management apparatus,
- 4) strengthening of monitoring working group,
- 5) the working group strengthening accountability for performance, and
- 6) working group meant to improve the quality of public services.

Based on the search results and the collection of primary data collected through the research that has been done in the field; Implementation of Legislative Reforms in South Kalimantan Province BKKBN generally look like the table below;

Table 4.1: Reforms in South Kalimantan Province BKKBN

No.	Pre Reforms	Reforms (Ideal/area change)	Reforms (Implementation)
1	Attendance manual (HR)	Mental Apparatus The high discipline and Work culture	Implementation of Attendance Finger ID (even now Face ID)
2	DP3 reporting in manuals	Increased Performance Apparatus	Reporting DP3 and SKP Online
3	No statements of work daily	Increased Performance Apparatus	Visum Reporting System Online (Sivika)

4	There is no concept of zones integrity/WBK (Accountability)	Bureaucracy clean and Accountable	The concept of socialization ZI/WBK continuous
5	Institutional structure (Bureaucracy) large	Effective bureaucracy (Mangkus) and Efficient (sangkil) (Institutional, become bureaucratic Structural Less More function (poor structure-function)	Bureaucratic structure still great
6	Low mindset and work culture	Mental Apparatus	There are no designated staff as an agent of change
7	Recruitment system still KKN	The increasing application of government clean and free of corruption	Level management free CPNS recruitment collusion and nepotism

Data source: Processed researches (2019).

Several factors were an obstacle in the implementation of bureaucratic reform policy in the office of South Kalimantan Province BKKBN Representative. The implementation of the theory is a variable implementation theory developed by George Edwards III. the theory has four variables that could affect the implementation of a policy:

A. Communication

The implementation of the reforms in South Kalimantan Province BKKBN has performing optimally helped by the use of the communication media, x- root banners and stickers. This is in conformity with the theory of Edwards III (Subarsono, 2005) "*The successful implementation of the policy requires so implementer know what to do. What are the goals and objectives of the policy must be transmitted to the target group (target group) that will reduce the distortion of policy implementation*".

Overall lack of communication leads to a lack of understanding of the importance of the implementation of bureaucratic reform; to create a good bureaucratic reform is required a strong commitment from leadership in the socialization of the integrity zone (ZI) and dissemination of the WBK (region free of corruption) as part of its commitment to the implementation of Reforms. The lack of communication and socialization can create a narrow understanding among ASN in South Kalimantan Province BKKBN environment.

However, ASN invited in the socialization not only the officials of administrators, officers of supervisors but also officials without involvement of the implementation. ZI and WBK communication was part of the commitment to the implementation of bureaucratic reform. Representative officers located in South Kalimantan Province BKKBN, held on almost every year, a coaching for the personnel on Employee Performance Goals (SKP).

SKP was used as a measurement of the performance of all individuals (ASN) working in Representative BKKBN South Kalimantan province.

Measurement of the SKP individual performance is part of the monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of the reform. Penetapan (individual performance)

assessment includes an application of individual performance evaluation. The test has been conducted on all employees; the achievement of individual performance has been used as the basis for the provision of performance benefits. But it is still not implemented in terms of competence in all officials in South Kalimantan Province BKKBN environment; only the officials who will occupy certain positions were included in the assessment.

The exclusion of all ASNs of Representatives BKKBN South Kalimantan Province in the socialization meeting mapping development ZI towards WBK/WBBM could have an impact on the lack of understanding, knowledge, insight, and information about the importance of reforms. In this case, the application of the Government is clean and free from corruption and also mangkus and sangkil.

B. Resources

Resources can be tangible, human resources, administrative civil state-owned by the South Kalimantan Province BKKBN. They comprise competence or expertise (skills), as well as financial resources/finance. The resource is an important factor to implement policies to run mangkus, as disclosed by George Edward III (Subarsono, 2005).

The resources consists in staff, expertise (specialization education) owned for implementing, relevant information, policies and compliance-related reserves, the authority which ensures that the program can be directed as a guided activity (terms of reference), as well as the support facilities which can be used to carry out a program of activities, such as money, time, labor, facilities and infrastructure (sarpras), human resources/personnel.

If the number of the executive staff is limited, then is necessary to increase the insight knowledge in order to carry out a program of activities. They include training, orientation, technical workshops, related duties and functions in the field. Other resources which are also important are the authority to determine how the program of activities carried out, the authority to carry out supervision and the support facilities necessary to carry out a policy.

Every office should have the necessary resources and supporting facilities. The resources management must be done by a leader in fostering the achievement of the performance contract for each year. The existing resources at the Representative Office of South Kalimantan Province BKKBN currently are composed by about 78 people. As level of education, there are 26 people (high school education), 3 (diploma), 35 (bachelor undergraduate) and 8 people (graduated).

Lack of ASN, especially the uneven distribution of ASN placed on a field will reduce overall performance and the performance of the relevant fields in carrying out their duties and functions. For example Field KS/PK at Representative office BKKBN South Kalimantan Province, only had 9 people ASN with only one person educated as graduate, compared with secretariat sector which has 24 people ASN consisting of 7 people high school educated, 1 with diploma three, 13 ASN degree 1 and 2 ASN degree.

C. Disposition/Attitude/Character

Disposition is the nature and characteristics possessed by the implementer, such as commitment, honesty, democratic sense. Disposition trait or attitude is one of the factors that influence kemangkusan policy implementation. If the implementor agrees with parts of the contents of the policy, then, of course, they will carry out wholeheartedly, but if it turns out that in their view is not good, then the implementation process will encounter many problems (Subarsono, 2005).

There are at least three form of implementor response to a policy;

- implementing awareness,
- guidance/assistance to respond towards the acceptance or rejection, and
- the intensity of the response.

The executor may understand the purpose and goals of the program, but often fail to implement appropriate action procedures, because of rejection of these activities, consequently, influence the budget absorption, it's unlikely that it diverts and evade implementation of the program. Then, the commitment of the administration officials (Echelon IV) depends on the commitment of high-ranking officials medium (Echelon II).

A strong commitment from the ASN to carry out the implementation of bureaucratic reform is starting from the highest leadership in the office.

Since the year 2010 to 2014 has been recorded three changes of the head of BKKBN Representative of South Kalimantan province. At that time the central level had issued the Regulation of the Head of BKKBN 131/KEP/B5/ 2011 on Bureaucracy Reform Team BKKBN.

During the second phase (2015-2019), until 2018 has been recorded three changes of the head of BKKBN Representative of South Kalimantan Province. On Reforms Implementation of the second phase at the central level have been issued Regulation of the BKKBN number 303 / PER / B4 / 2015 on the Road Map Reforms BKKBN Year 2015-2019, which then updated with Chief Regulation No. 9 of 2017 on Reforms Roadmap.

The regulation was strengthened by the decision of the Head of BKKBN number 304/KEP/B4/2015 dated December 23, 2015, on Bureaucracy Reform Team BKKBN, which subsequently updated by the Decree of the Head of BKKBN No. 87/KEP/B4/2017 on Bureaucracy Reform Team. The second-period Implementation of Reforms in South Kalimantan Province BKKBN office, precisely on January 29, 2018, the Decree of the Head of South Kalimantan Province BKKBN No. 15/HK.02.02/J1/2018 on Representative Bureaucracy Reform Team BKKBN South Kalimantan province.

As a change of the head of South Kalimantan Province, BKKBN representatives became the main trigger. Therefore, if there is no legal basis at the provincial level, then there will be problems in the form of ineffectiveness.

D. Bureaucratic structure

One important aspect of the structure of any organization is the standard operating procedures (SOP). They are characteristics, norms, and patterns of relationships that occur repeatedly, executive bodies that have a potential or real relationship with what

they have in carrying out the policy. In this bureaucratic structure, variables include the supervision, monitoring, and attention superiors to subordinates.

According to investigators, the institutional arrangement is a relationship among units that govern how these can cooperate or compete. Generally, the definition of institutions includes the concept of social behavior patterns entrenched, ongoing or recurring.

The structure of the organization is done by BKKBN, among others; by evaluating the organization, which conducts to a comprehensive manner following the stages in the context of organizational structuring. To reach the desired direction, the concept of organizational structuring BKKBN adopts a customer-based orientation. Modern organization relies on efficiency and effectiveness (*kemangkusan*) so that each box structure will focus on the function of production, marketing, sales, and after-sales to mobilize stakeholders and partners.

Each of the functions (production, marketing, sales and post-sales) are expected to support each other in implementing strategies to achieve the goals through mobilization. The division of functions and authority of organizational units will facilitate human resources in BKKBN in carrying out its duties and responsibilities. They will also be easier down the performance targets as well as in measurement. These descriptions will be easier to formulate or develop into the desired organizational model.

Based on data retrieval and information that researchers gathered, the efforts to strengthen the structure of bureaucracy do BKKBN include evaluations that have been conducted to analyze the possibility of duplication of functions. The evaluations have been conducted to analyze the organizational units of different purpose but are placed in the same group. Based on the evaluation, there are different work unit objectives which are placed in one group, for example at law and public relations bureau.

BKKBN has evaluated the organization in order to analyze the possibility of overlapping functions with other agencies. Bureaucratic structure changes, results of evaluations have been followed up by proposing changes Bureaucratic Structure, evidenced by Letter of the Minister of PAN and RB to the head of BKKBN number: B/3610/M.PANRB/09/2014 dated September 29, 2014, concerning the Draft Amendment BKKBN Head of Organization and Work Procedures BKKBN; and Enactment of Regulations Head of BKKBN number: 273/PER/B4/2014 on Amendments to the Perka BKKBN number 72/PER/B5/2011 on Organization and Work procedures BKKBN; Proposed Changes To Menpan Letter No. 1724/OT.402/B4/2015 on Petition Facilitation Institutional Restructuring BKKBN.

In September of 2018 was still not issued a new Decree of the Head of BKKBN about bureaucratic structure (organization) BKKBN. Its elaboration begins with the attachment of the action plan, it can be concluded that the possibility of changes in the organizational structure, work procedures, and standard operating procedures in the BKKBN is still in the drafting process.

Government institutions are considered that are not running mangkus (effective) and sangkil (efficient). Therefore, changes in the institutional system will promote efficiency, effectiveness, and will accelerate the process of service and decision making in the bureaucracy reform. Changes to the institutional system are expected to encourage the creation of a culture/behavior that is more conducive to realizing an effective and efficient bureaucracy.

4. Conclusion

At provincial level, the Head of BKKBN released the decision No. 87/KEP/B4/2017 on Bureaucracy Reform Team followed up with the release of Decision of the Chief Representative, South Kalimantan Province BKKBN No. 15/HK.02:02/J1/2018 on Bureaucracy Reform Team BKKBN South Kalimantan province.

However, since the issuance of the decision, has not been done the meeting of the working group. However, the working group team effectively worked only one year in carrying out its duties. Therefore, the implementation of the second phase of bureaucratic reform will end in 2019. So how could the working group team perform their duties mangkus (effective) and sangkil (efficient) if the establishment was held one year before the end of the second phase of bureaucratic reform, and since the formation there has never been a coordination meeting? Frequent change of the head of South Kalimantan Province BKKBN representatives became the main trigger. This resulted in a lack of mangkus and sangkil in reform policy implementation. Lack of ASN, especially, uneven distribution of ASN will reduce overall performance and the performance of the relevant fields in carrying out their duties and functions.

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